

**EFFECT OF BOARD INDEPENDENCE AND SIZE ON FINANCIAL DISTRESS
OF LISTED CONSUMER GOODS FIRMS IN NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of board independence and size on the financial distress of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria for fifteen years (2009–2023). Published annual reports were used as secondary data from the sampled firms. The population consists of 13 consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange as of 31st December 2023, and the sample size was made up of 13 consumer goods firms having the required data. Atman's Z-score was used to measure FD. The study adopted the multiple regression technique in analyzing the data extracted. The study concluded that board size and board independence show significant effects on the financial distress of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Based on these findings, this study recommends that the presence of independent directors on the board should be encouraged, as they will enhance monitoring mechanisms and reduce the propensity to likelihood of financial distress. Additionally, the board size is recommended to be sizable enough to have good management skills and different experiences to develop and perform the leading role and responsibilities to achieve effective governance.

Keywords: Board independence, Board Size, Financial distress likelihood

1. Introduction

Board characteristics and financial distress are important issues in the consumer goods business, financial sector, and even other sectors of the Nigerian economy because of their importance to major stakeholders like creditors, financial analysts and potential investors. However, according to Ogbeta and Torbira (2014), board characteristics /management quality is a crucial performance indicator of a company's financial distress. a reference to the early years of the twenty-first century, when a string of high-profile crises including the global financial crisis of 2009 caused financial distress as a result of subpar corporate governance, including the accounting scandals including Bacita sugar company in 2006, Nigeria paper converter company 2002, World Com Inc. in 2002, Arthur Anderson in 2002 and Enron Inc. in 2001.

The trust that investors and stakeholders have in financial statements has been impacted by these scandals and crises. Additionally, the revelations that followed these scandals and crises brought the importance of the quality of financial statements and the application of accounting principles like the going concern principle to the attention of regulators and researchers (Zureigat, 2011). Financial statements are generally both helpful and trustworthy when other accounting standards, including the going concerns principle, are used.

In Nigerian businesses, particularly Consumer goods corporations, financial difficulties or corporate bankruptcy have been a frequent occurrence (Taliani & Sedrine, 2010). Due to the frequent occurrences of business failure, which have caught the attention of investors and other stakeholders, it is necessary to determine the primary reason for corporate bankruptcy. Since corporate governance is a mechanism by which the affairs of the organization are managed and controlled by the directors, it is necessary to examine the top management and internal control system of the organization to ascertain the essence of corporate governance regarding the financial distress of such companies. An entity's ability to continue operating or maintain its existence is impacted by financial distress. The going concern concept, which states that the financial statements have been prepared based on the possibility that the company would continue to do its regular operations indefinitely, is one of the fundamental accounting principles in this context. Going concern refers to the presumption that a company will carry on with its operations for the foreseeable future without the need or purpose of going out of business, suspending operations, or seeking protection from creditors in accordance with laws or regulations. The job of external auditors becomes extremely important in assessing the company's ability to continue operating when it encounters any financial challenges, such as the inability to fulfill its obligations and suffer losses. Users of financial statements will have their interests protected, and it will assist them in making investment decisions.

The responsibility of ensuring proper financial health rests on the shoulder of the apex governing body of a firm “the board of directors”. Furthermore, the foremost aim of financial reporting activity is to make available true financial position and performance; while corporate governance as part of objective, provides a platform to ensure that the financial reports published is a reflection of the true financial position of the company. The link between corporate governance and financial distress has been intensely discussed in developed countries with scarce evidence from emerging economies like Nigeria (Uwuigbe et al., 2017). Consequently; there is no conclusive evidence on the effect of corporate governance on the financial distress as proxy by board size and board independence.

There are many studies that have examined the effect of corporate governance on the financial distress globally but only few of them have been conducted in Nigeria such as Aliyu and Babatunde (2017), Oreoluwa, and Imene (2016), Uwalomwa, et al. (2018), however, to the best of the researcher's knowledge none of these studies have used the consumer goods firms of the Nigerian exchange as a domain, therefore making this study different and unique.

In addition, the works of Aliyu and Babatunde (2017), Oreoluwa and Imene (2016) and Uwalomwa, et al. (2018) did not extend their data period coverage beyond 2017, following the spite of financial distress there is need to extend the period of these studies to year 2021. This creates a period gap which this study intends to fill by investigating the work to 2021. The period is also extended to fifteen years (15) for a more robust data analysis. This creates a gap for further study. Therefore, the study aims to examine the effect of board independence and board size on financial distress of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria for the period of 2009 to 2023. The study's specific objectives are to identify the effect of board size and board independence on financial distress of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

The following hypotheses were formulated in null form based on the above specific objectives;

- H₀₁ Board Independence (BIND) has no significant effect on financial distress of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria
- H₀₂ Board Size (BS) has no significant effect on financial distress of listed consumer

goods companies in Nigeria.

This research will be of eminent assistance to Nigerian makers of policy such as Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and other stakeholders in charge of regulating various industries. The study will also assist investors and financial analyst to make an informed decision regarding corporate governance mechanism in quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and ensure investment opportunities are entered into with certainty. In addition, this study will enable finance managers, management accountants, academia, and students who will be interested in this study to meet their different need. It will also add value to the existing literature on corporate governance and financial distress.

The study covers fifteen years' period (2009-2023). This period is considered reasonable due to the speedy economic recovery and growth witnessed in the Nigerian stock market from 2000 to 2009 and a declined and fluctuations from mid-2009 up to 2017. The choice of listed Nigerian consumer goods firms as a domain is informed by the fact that it would facilitate easy access to financial statements of the companies to be studied. Using data from such sources could enhance the reliability and validity of data used. The remaining part of the study is separated into four segments dealing with the discussion on the review of literature and theoretical issues, the research method, the results and discussions as well as the conclusion and recommendation.

2. Literature Review

This segment reviewed the literature on board independence, board size and financial distress under three major headings namely: Conceptual review, Empirical studies and Theoretical issues.

Financial Distress

Financial distress is a state in which a company is compelled to take remedial action because its operating cash flows are insufficient to pay its present obligations (Ross et al., 2005). Financial difficulty, according to Altman (1968), Whitaker (1999), and Mumford (2003), occurs when a corporation is unable to pay its debts. The absence or reduction of dividend payments along with violations of financial covenants are typically the first signs of difficulty. Whitaker (1999) and Wruck (1990) claim that companies experience financial distress as a result of economic distress brought on by a fall in industry operating income and bad management as a result of persistently low operating income over a five-year period. Financial distress was measured by Atman's Z-score

Usdin and Bloom (2012) identified nine indicators of financial distress, including the company's failure to pay creditors on time, being sued for unpaid debts, experiencing a significant event that won't happen again, having a union threaten legal action against the company, having a major supplier threaten to stop providing services to the company, and failing to meet its contractual obligations. Prior research links financial parameters like leverage, profitability, liquidity, and asset turnover to financial crisis (Zulkarnain & Hasbullah, 2009). According to Amoa (2014), highly leveraged companies may go bankrupt if they are unable to make their repayment obligations, but they also run the risk of increasing shareholder return on investment. Profitability and liquidity play a direct role in a company's resilience through difficult times. According to Parker et al. (2002), these ratios are predicted to have a bad correlation with the likelihood of financial trouble.

Board Independence

A director who is independent is one who is not related to the board of directors, a member of

another board of directors, or a controlling shareholder. Independent directors are also free from any business or other relationships that might limit their ability to act impartially or in the company's best interests. An independent director is, in essence, one who is unconnected financially or familiarly to the other directors or shareholders. In essence, every filmmaker works for themselves. This indicates that employees must be able to perform their jobs without interference, understand the company's interests, and be free from any influences that have interests that are at odds with those of the company (Abdulkarim et al., 2020).

Board independence is based on how many members are not already associated with the company through employment or other forms of financial exchange (Gordon, 2007). A board is more independent if it has more independent members and if its chair is not the same person who serves as the company's CEO (Gaur et al., 2015). Independent boards are often regarded as advantageous because they are more difficult for top management to control and because they may be more inclined to support reforms even in the face of resistance from management, according to Dowell et al. (2011). To ensure their ability to exercise independent judgment in managerial oversight, the UK Corporate Governance Code (2012) requires that a board be predominantly made of independent directors (Hsu & Wu, 2014).

Independent directors are in a better position to monitor and control potential opportunism and avoid selfish behavior of management because they have no other connection to the company than their position on the board (Fama & Jensen 1983; Jensen 1993). This helps to ensure that their decisions are in line with the interests of shareholders. Therefore, independent directors, who are less likely to engage in actions that diminish shareholder value, are better suited to perform supervisory duties, according to Fama and Jensen (1983).

The presence of independent directors on the board, according to Fich and Slezak (2008) and Chang (2009), minimizes the possibility of information asymmetries and the costs of agency between shareholders and management, which have an impact on a company's financial health. Since they are more effective at enforcing the necessary measures to overcome a potential distress situation, companies with a higher percentage of independent directors on their boards are therefore less likely to experience financial distress (Pregio de la Cruz et al., 2014). Any company needs a board of directors that is capable of both effective monitoring and strategic vision. The potential importance of board independence has been highlighted in numerous research on the operation and effectiveness of boards of directors (Karpoff et al., 2017).

The proportion of independent directors reflects the level of board oversight, but it is insufficient to demonstrate the effectiveness of such scrutiny or the ability of a board to provide management with knowledgeable advice. According to Black and Khanna (2015), outside directors with executive experience are essential for the growth of shareholder value, and executives from other local businesses make up a sizable portion of independent directors and the local pool of potential directors. Corporate boards require independent directors to have specific knowledge and skills to support the board and CEO in addition to general management expertise (Linck et al., 2018).

Board Size

Board size is the term used to describe the number of directors on a board of directors. There are two schools of thinking regarding board size small and large but it is unclear which is superior. A small board of directors contributes more to a company's performance, according to scholars in the first school of thought (Yermack, 2016). Furthermore, according to

Yermack (2016), a large board wastes time and makes decisions slowly, which impairs communication and hurts the performance of the company. According to the second school of thought, a bigger board of directors improves business performance and enables it to gather more data. Only if there are enough board members to fill out those tasks will a firm's board be able to devote enough time to multiple duties (O'Sullivan, 2009).

The number of directors on boards should be increased or decreased, according to research (Daily et al., 2003; Fich & Slezak, 2008). A larger board of directors is required to increase the disciplinary control over the CEO since, according to Simpson and Gleason (1999), a CEO will find it difficult to influence a larger board of directors (Brédart, 2014). Larger boards are thought to provide the CEO with better counsel, according to Dalton et al. (1999). Another benefit of larger boards is the ability of the company to utilize the resources and knowledge possessed by the directors that may be necessary to achieve firm objectives. These show that businesses with larger boards are more successful in avoiding financial distress.

Larger boards are preferred because they may provide businesses with more channels for communicating with outside stakeholders who manage the resources needed for operations (Abeysekera, 2010). Due to this diversity, boards with members who have a wider range of educational backgrounds and work experience are more likely to provide management with recommendations of the highest caliber (Zahra & Peace, 1989). As a result, the company's reputation and relationships with stakeholders might be enhanced. The function of board size has been controversial from a number of angles. It is said that the monitoring, decision-making, and disclosure processes are impacted by the board's size.

Board size is important for corporate monitoring, and according to Mallin (2002), as board size increases, efficiency declines because decision-making moves more slowly. However, Spong and Sullivan (2017) argued that size is unrelated to company value by asserting that size is dependent on each individual business's age, size, and need for guidance and supervision. However, according to Jensen (1993), the demand for smaller board sizes is a result of organizational and technical advancement, which ultimately leads to cost-cutting and downsizing. Bigger boards may not be as successful as smaller boards, according to Hermalin and Weisbach (2013). Agency problems may become more common on boards with an overwhelming number of members.

Review of Empirical Studies

Board Independence and Financial Distress

Muslifiansyah et al. (2022) examined the effect of the independent board of commissioners and motivation on financial distress. The study sampled 26 transport companies in Indonesia for period 2019 to 2022. Multiple linear regression models were used to identify how independent variables influence the likelihood of financial distress. The result shows that independent board of commissioners does not significantly increase the likelihood of financial distress in the companies.

Munene et al. (2020) examined the influence of board characteristics on financial distress of deposit taking SACCOS in Nairobi-Kenya. The study sampled 43 companies for period 2012-2018 using panel regression analysis. The result revealed that larger board size has detrimental effect on financial distress. The study also documented negative significant effect of board independence on financial distress. However, the study differs with the findings of Maina and Omagwa (2020) who documented positive insignificant effect of independent directorship on financial distress when they studied board characteristics and financial distress of listed commercial banks in Kenya. The study sampled 11 banks for period 2011-2018 using panel regression analysis.

Humairoh and Nurulita (2020) investigated the effect of corporate governance on financial distress in Indonesia. The study sampled 13 companies for the period of 2015-2020 using multiple regression analysis. The result revealed positive and negative insignificant effect of board size and independent commissioners respectively. This means that number of directors on board and higher percentage of independent directors cannot reduce or increase the possibility of financial distress in the sampled companies. This was confirmed by Anning et al. (2021) who investigated the effect of board of directors characteristics on the likelihood of Ghanaian listed Banks experiencing financial distress for period of 2010 – 2017 for 11 listed banks. Board size and non-executive board insignificantly affected financial distress.

Using panel data consisting of 2519 listed non-financial enterprises from 29 different European countries between the years of 2012 and 2020, Maier et al. (2022) investigated how board features affect the likelihood of bankruptcy. The study found that a lower chance of insolvency is associated with board independence. Conversely, it is expected that employee representatives will increase the risk of insolvency and negatively affect the board's oversight capacity. Two measures of board diversity that reduce the risk of bankruptcy are the presence of international and female directors. For financially troubled companies, on the other hand, board diversity and independence actually increase the risk of bankruptcy. These are statistically and economically significant results that hold, at least partially, for other specifications. Our findings indicate that, particularly in the event of impending financial hardship, governance regulators, credit rating agencies, financial institutions, businesses, and investors should give board composition more thought.

Shahab et al. (2020) focused on family-run enterprises and concentrated ownership when examining the relationship between board structure features and the likelihood of financial distress for an emerging economy's non-financial sector. In the current study, panel logistic regression was utilized to determine the correlation between board structure characteristics and the probability of financial hardship. The Altman Z-Score was used as a stand-in for the likelihood of firm financial distress because it measures financial likelihood inversely. The study finds a significant relationship between board size and the likelihood of financial difficulties. The results showed that a one-unit increase in board size would lead to a 3.4% decrease in the probability of financial difficulties. Furthermore, we discover that a higher degree of board independence is linked to a lower likelihood of financial distress.

Kenedy et al. (2018) looked into the significance of independent directors in trying financial times. The research methodology used in this study was exploratory. Using panel regression analysis, pooled regression, and random effects, the study examined 39 listed firms in Kenya between 2004 and 2013. The study found a strong and negative correlation ($p=0.05$; $=-0.044$) between the likelihood of financial distress and board independence. This study advances theory by performing an empirical analysis of the influence of independent directors on the likelihood of financial distress. This study fills a significant knowledge gap by focusing on an emerging nation and providing insights into the function of independent directors in challenging economic times. This study is meant to be read in conjunction with others that focus on the Middle East or China. In light of the growing number of company failures in emerging economies, this research also provides evidence to policy makers regarding the implications of board independence for financial sustainability.

Board Size and Financial Distress

The impact of board size on the likelihood of financial distress for companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) was investigated by Maranjory and Tajani (2022). A distinct set of data obtained from the financial statements' content analysis over a five-year period

between 2016 and 2020. With the aid of EViews 8 software, a multivariate linear regression model with panel data was employed for the data analysis. The random effect was determined to be appropriate for the study by the Hausman test, which is used to choose between fixed and random effects models. The study's conclusions showed that the likelihood of financial distress is negatively impacted by board size, with no discernible effect. This demonstrates that the caliber of the board members holds greater significance than their numerical count. Nonetheless, the research is restricted to Tehran, and the conclusions and suggestions are not applicable to the Nigerian context, which is why the study was required.

Afenya et al. (2022) assessed the impact of board size on the financial distress of Ghanaian publicly traded companies. Secondary data was extracted from the financial statements of companies registered on the Ghana Stock Exchange from the period of 2008 to 2019. The population of the study is 38 companies and the sample size is 25 listed companies traded on the Ghanaian stock market. The study used a multivariate ordinary least square regression with fixed effect purposely to control for various firm-level heterogeneity features that could affect the empirical relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable. The study findings found that board size has a substantial negative impact on financial distress. From the reviewed study, the research was limited to Ghana and the findings and recommendations may not apply to Nigeria due to the difference codes of corporate governance guidelines and the Company and Allied Matter Act of the two countries.

Nouraldeen et al. (2021) examined the factors that influence the likelihood of financial distress in developing Middle Eastern countries like Lebanon by focusing on the Lebanese context. From 2012 to 2017, a sample of Lebanese commercial banks operating in Lebanon is used for the study. The investigation found that multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the extracted data. The results of the study indicate that board size has a statistically significant negative impact on the likelihood of financial distress. Nigeria might not be able to extrapolate the study's findings about the implications of Middle East policy because of its limited scope.

Mobarak et al. (2021) examined the effect of board size on financial distress of non-financial Saudi-listed companies between the period of 2015 and 2018. From the 125 listed companies, a sample of 99 companies from 16 sectors was selected due to incomplete or ambiguous data. Poisson regression analysis was used to analysis the extracted panel data. The findings of the study established that board size has a positive and insignificant effect on financial distress. Based on the reviewed study, the research is limited to a foreign context for a period of 4 years. This, however, has a limited year to generalize or conclude the financial distress of a company. In addition, the findings of the study cannot be generalized to Nigeria context due to diversity in policy and regulation among others. This, therefore, necessitated this study.

Ovbiebo (2021) assesses the effect of board size on financial distress among Nigeria-listed insurance companies. Twenty (20) quoted insurance companies in the Nigeria Stock Exchange as of 31st December 2020 and the sample of five (5) listed Insurance companies were obtained from their respective annual reports covering the period 2016 to 2020. A convenient sampling technique was used in the study. A secondary source of panel data was collected and content analysis was employed in the study. The panel Least Square (PLS) regression estimation techniques were used to analysis the data. The study found that board size (ACS) has an insignificant positive effect on financial distress in the insurance sub-sector

of the Nigerian economy. The study is limited to only 5 insurance companies for 5 years, while my study will be focusing on consumer goods firms in Nigeria over a period of 10 years.

Theoretical Issues

The theory underpinning this study is Stakeholders Theory.

The stakeholder theory is a theory that looks at how a company interacts with its stakeholders. The stakeholder approach was first used, and since then, it has developed into a consistent aspect of corporate life that is now challenging to ignore in any corporate model (Andriof & Waddock, 2002). While Donaldson & Preston (1995) defined stakeholders as people or groups with legitimate interests in the procedural and/or substantive aspects of corporate activity, Freeman (1984) defined stakeholders as any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the firm's objectives (Shafiq et al., 2014).

A main goal of the stakeholder theory, according to Logdson and Wood (2000), is to assist corporate managers in comprehending their stakeholder environments and managing more skillfully within the web of connections that exists for their organizations. Stakeholder theory, according to Mitchell et al. (1997), strives to expand management's understanding of its role and responsibilities beyond profit-maximizing activities to encompass interests and claims of non-shareholder groups.

Stakeholder theory emphasizes a firm's accountability beyond just economic or financial performance, so a firm must meet the multiple expectations of various stakeholder groups rather than just the expectations of shareholders as in the traditional shareholder theories. Thus, stakeholder theory provides a framework for identifying important groups to which a company should direct its social efforts and serves as a basis for understanding the correlation between different measures of firm performance (Jones, 1995).

3 Methodology

Longitudinal research design was adopted in measuring the effect of corporate governance mechanism on financial distress of listed consumer goods forms in Nigeria for the period 2009 to 2023. This study population consist of consumer goods companies listed in Nigeria, as at 31st December 2023 there were twenty-three consumer goods companies listed in the Nigerian Exchange. Hence, the study excludes companies with incomplete financial annual reports during the period under study. The population of this study consists of twenty-three consumer goods companies listed in Nigeria and thirteen consumer goods companies annual financial report were available on the Nigerian Exchange during the period under study from 1st January 2009 to 31st December 2023.

The list of consumer goods firms listed in Nigerian Exchange (NGX).

Table 1 Population and sample size of the study

S/N	Name of Company	Year of Listing	Sample
1	Cadbury Nigeria plc	1976	Selected
2	Champion Breweries Plc	1983	Not Selected
3	Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc	2007	Selected
4	Flour Mills of Nigeria Plc	1979	Selected
5	Guinness Nigeria Plc	1965	Selected

6	Honeywell Flour Mill Plc	2009	Not selected
7	International Breweries Plc	1995	Selected
8	McNichols Plc	2009	Not selected
9	Nascon Allied Industries Plc	1992	Selected
10	Nestle Nigeria Plc	1979	Selected
11	Nigeria Breweries Plc	1973	Selected
12	Nigerian Enamelware Plc	1979	Selected
13	Northern Nigerian Flour Mill Plc	1978	Selected
14	PZ Cussons Nigeria Plc	1974	Selected
15	Tantalizer Plc.	2021	Not selected
16	Unilever Nigeria Plc	1973	Selected
17	Vita foam Nigeria Plc	1978	Selected
18	Dangote Flour Mills Plc	2008	Not selected
19	Multi-Trek Integrated Food Plc	2010	Not selected
20	Union Dicon Salt Plc	1993	Not selected
21	Golden Guinea Breweries Plc	1979	Not selected
22	7-Up Bottling Company Plc	1986	Not selected
23	DN Tyre & rubber plc	1961	Not selected

Source: Field work (2024)

Model Specification

The model specification to be used in this study will be based on the explanation of the relationship between the dependent and independent variable of this research. Therefore, the multiple regression is defined as

$$FL_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BIND_{it} + \beta_3 FS_{it} + \beta_4 LEV_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where : FL_i = represents financial distress which is the dependent variable;

BS = Board Size

BIND = Board independence

FS= Firm Size

LEV= Leverage

i = number of companies, t = the index of time periods =15 ϵ =is the error component for company

β_0 = Intercept of the model “Constant”, $\beta = 1, 2 \dots$ are parameters to be estimated

Variables, Definitions and Measurements

Table 2

Variable, definition and measurements

Variable	Type	Measurements	Sources
Financial Distress (FD)	Dependent	Altman Z-score	Altman et al. (2006)
Board Independence (BIND)	Independent	Percentage of independent directors to total number of directors in the board	Morellec (2012)
Board Size (BS)	Independent Control	Number of directors on the board.	Horváth & Spirollari (2012)

Firm Size (FS)	Control	Natural log of total asset	Alhares et al. (2020)
Leverage (LEV)		Total debt to total company assets	Anwar et al. (2019)

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

Financial distress (FD) is a situation in which the selected firms find itself unable to meet financial obligations. It is measured as:

$$FD = Z\text{-Score} = \frac{ROAA + ETA}{\alpha ROAA}$$

Where :

ROAA = The firms return on average assets

ETA = Equity to total assets

α ROAA= Standard deviation of return on average Assets

Z- Score = Financial distress

4. Results and Discussion

This section describes the data presentation, analysis and interpretation. The section consists of descriptive analysis, diagnostic tests, regression analyses, hypotheses testing and discussion of findings. The data for the paper's model is in Appendix A1. Appendices B1 to B3 are the raw STATA results derived from the data in Appendix A1. Table 1 presents the results of descriptive statistics showing the observations, the mean, standard deviation, minimum mean and maximum mean.

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
FD	195	2.626044	1.147108	.1111	4.9202
BS	195	8.94359	2.483325	4	14
BIND	195	64.23303	13.32063	40	90
FZ	195	7.58559	.696677	5.8	8.74
LEV	195	63.24718	23.96276	12.42	305.8

Source: Stata 17.0 Results Output

Table 3 shows a detailed analysis of the financial distress (FD) among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The number of observations is 195, which was obtained by multiplying the number of listed consumer goods firms (13) by the number of years covered by the study (15).

Also, the central mean of FD (Financial distress) was 2.626 with a standard deviation of

1.1467. Showing there is little dispersion of the variable from their mean. Indicating that consumer goods company's rate of financial distress is low. This suggests the need for comprehensive regulatory measures and strategic planning to mitigate the financial distress. Furthermore, the minimum mean is 0.1111 and the maximum mean is 4.9202. This suggests that firms with exceptional low Financial distress (FD) values are at the risk of financial distress and require immediate support. Consumer goods firms with high value of FD values indicates financial stability.

Furthermore, the central mean of BS (board size) was 8.928 with a standard deviation of 2.483. By comparison, the standard deviation is lower than the central mean, suggesting that board size is not too explosive. Furthermore, the minimum mean is 4 and the maximum mean is 14. This suggests that some firms have 4 board members, which is less than the minimum 8 board members recommended by the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code. The maximum board size was 14, it should be noted that while the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code did suggest a minimum board size, it did not recommend any maximum limit. Also, board independence (BIND) shows a central mean of about 64 per cent with a standard deviation of about 13 per cent. By a way of comparison, the standard deviation is less than the central mean, suggesting that the level of volatility among the firms and the periods of coverage is low. Also, the minimum mean is 40 per cent and the maximum mean is 90 per cent. Note that board independence means the fraction of non-executive directors expressed to total board size.

Table 3 further shows the control variable Firm size (FS) has mean of 7.586. This implies that firms are not similar in sizes as indicated in the table showing maximum is larger than the mean. Some of the consumer goods companies are large while some are smaller companies. It also shows minimum and maximum mean values of 5.8 and 8.74 percent and standard deviation of .697 respectively. Finally, Table 3 shows leverage (LEV) has mean of 63.247 percent with a standard deviation 23.963. The average value revealed that some of the consumer goods companies are highly geared while the standard deviation suggested that the companies leverage level followed the same pattern. It also shows minimum and maximum of 12.42 and 305.8 percent of debt respectively.

Results of Diagnostic Checks

Pre and post diagnostic test are carried out to check the robustness of the data in other to know the validity of the linear regression model's statistical inference. Robustness checks carried out under this study are Multicollinearity test and Heteroscedasticity of residuals.

The results of multicollinearity test are reported in Table 4

Table 4

Variance inflation factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
FZ	1.17	0.858179
BIND	1.10	0.906745
LEV	1.09	0.918852
BS	1.03	0.967197
<i>Mean VIF 1.10</i>		

Source: Stata 17.0 Results Output

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance Values (TV) are shown in Table 4.

Following the figures in Table 4 indicating 1.17 as the highest variance inflation factor (VIF) it is clear that there is no problem of multicollinearity among the dependent, independent and control variables and therefore the study can go ahead to use a parametric method.

The results of heteroskedasticity test are reported in Table 5

Table 5

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variable: Fitted values of FD

Chi2 (1) = 11.60

Prob > chi2 = 0.1085

Source: Stata 17.0 Results Output

As indicated in Table 5, the p-value of heteroskedasticity is not significant (0.1085), meaning that it is higher than .05 level of significance. This suggests that there is no heteroskedasticity in the model.

Table 6

Regression Result Analysis

FD	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P>t	[95% conf.	interval]
BS	-.0715658	.0305605	-2.34	0.020	-.1318473	-.0112843
BIND	-.0287851	.0058842	-4.89	0.000	-.0403918	-.0171785
FZ	.5928139	.1156463	5.13	0.000	.3646984	.8209294
LEV	.0101191	.0032493	3.11	0.002	.0037097	.0165284
_cons	-.0217895	.9513559	-0.02	0.982	-1.898366	1.854787
R-squared	0.1956					
Adj R-squared	0.1787					
Prob > F	0.0000					

Source: STATA 17 Outputs.

Table 5 indicate the various levels and degree of impact of board independence and board size on financial distress. The R squared value of 0.1956 shows the predictive power of the model. This indicates that, about 0.1956 variation in the FD of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria is explained by BS and BIND. Generally, the model of the study is robust as the p-value of the model is significant at 0.05.

Specifically, board size (BS) with a coefficient of -.0715658 and a p-value of 0.020 shows that board size has a significant relationship with financial distress of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, given that the p-value is less than the 5% threshold. Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that board size has a significant effect on financial distress. This result is consistent with a priori expectations of this study. This finding is in line with prior empirical studies of Maranjory and Tajani (2022), and Afenya et al. (2022) reveal a significant effect of board size on financial distress. However, on the contrary, Ovbiebo (2020) and Mobarak et al. (2021), which reveal that there is no correlation between board size and financial distress.

Furthermore, Board Independence was indicated with a coefficient value of -.0287851 and a p-value of 0.000. This shows that BIND is statistically significant at 0.000, as the p-value is lower than 5%. Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis. Therefore, the study is

supported by the work of Kenedy et al. (2018) and Maier et al. (2022). Which reveals that there is a correlation between board independence and financial distress.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The research examined the effect of board independence and board size on financial distress of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study concluded that board size, has a significant effect on financial distress of consumer goods firms in Nigeria, additionally, BIND is also significantly influencing financial distress of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Board size is recommended to be sizeable enough to have good management skills, different experience to develop and perform the leading role and responsibilities in other to achieved effective governance. The study further recommends that the presence of independent director on the board should be encouraged as they will enhance monitoring mechanism and reduce the principal agent conflicts in the organization.

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